

Synthesis of Indole-2-carboxaldehydes, 2-(2-Aminoethyl)- and 2-(2-Aminopropyl) indoles

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A number of *Bz*-halogen substituted ethyl indole-2-carboxylates have been reduced with lithium aluminium hydride to get the corresponding 2-hydroxymethylindoles; the latter were oxidised with activated manganese dioxide and the resulting indole-2-carboxaldehydes reacted with nitromethane and nitroethane. The condensation products on reduction with lithium aluminium hydride gave 2-(2-aminoethyl)- and 2-(2-aminopropyl) indoles respectively.

WHITTLE and Young¹ suggested that the substitution in the aromatic ring of tryptamine by halogen atom particularly in the 5 and 6 positions might be expected to produce metabolic block resulting in sustaining drug action. Further,

introduction of halogen atom would also tend to increase the drug persistence by increasing the solubility in the lipid material of the body. Some α -alkyltryptamines reported by the above workers were found to possess stimulant and anticonvulsant

R = a; 4-Cl
c; 6-Cl
e; 5-Br
g; 5-Me, 7-Cl
i; 5-Br, 7-Me

b; 5-Cl
d; 7-Cl
f; 7-Br
h; 5-Cl, 7-Me

properties in rodents and to produce behaviour changes in cats. Some *Bz*-halosubstituted 1-(3-aminopropyl) indoles synthesised in our laboratory² were found to be more potent antagonists of serotonin than BAS. Similarly, out of the several *Bz*-halo and methylsubstituted tryptamines reported by Ambekar and Siddappa^{3a,b}, 5-chloro-7-*N,N*-trimethyltryptamine caused 50% inhibition to the serotonin contractile action in as low a concentration as 0.7 $\mu\text{g/ml}^{3c}$.

Considering these facts, it seemed interesting to extend our previous work⁴ on indole-2-carboxaldehydes, 2-(2-aminoethyl)- and 2-(2-aminopropyl) indoles to the *Bz*-halogen substituted compounds, with the hope of obtaining more potent antiserotonin drugs.

Indole-2-carboxaldehydes required as intermediates for the synthesis of the title compounds were prepared by the oxidation of 2-hydroxymethylindoles with activated manganese dioxide according to Harley-Mason and Pavri⁵ (Cf. ref. 4). Ethyl 4-chloroindole-2-carboxylate (Ia) was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride⁶ to get 4-chloro-2-hydroxymethylindole (IIa) which upon oxidation with activated manganese dioxide yielded 4-chloroindole-2-carboxaldehyde (IIIa). The oxidation reaction was followed by TLC and was found to take 12–15 hr. The method was extended to the synthesis of other indole-2-carboxaldehydes (IIIa-i) described in Table 2. The indole-2-carboxaldehydes reacted readily with nitromethane to yield 2-(2-nitrovinyl) indoles (IVa-i), and on reduction with lithium aluminium hydride gave the desired 2-(2-aminoethyl) indoles (Va-i). Similarly, condensation of the aldehydes (IIIa,b and d-i) with nitroethane furnished 2-(2-nitropropenyl) indoles (VIa,b and d-i) which on subsequent reduction with lithium aluminium hydride gave the required 2-(2-aminopropyl) indoles (VIIa,b and d-i).

The u.v. and i.r. spectra of 2-hydroxymethylindoles (IIa-i), indole-carboxaldehydes (IIIa-i), 2-(2-nitrovinyl) indoles (IVa-i) and 2-(2-nitropropenyl) indoles (VIa,b and d-i) have been recorded.

During the course of the present investigation it was observed that the 2-(2-nitrovinyl) indoles (IVa-i) and 2-(2-nitropropenyl) indoles (VIa,b and d-i) did not show the expected i.r. absorption band due to the nitro group. On the other hand, the compounds exhibited new bands near 1270 and 1223 cm^{-1} . Similarly, the u.v. spectra showed strong absorption in the 400 nm region. Similar types of compounds described in the previous paper⁴ also exhibited same type of spectroscopic behaviour. This observation suggested an inner nitronium salt structure for these nitrovinylindoles and nitropropenylindoles, as shown below :

Our observations are in agreement with the earlier reports^{1,8}.

Experimental

Ultraviolet spectra were recorded in Hilger Uvispek H-700 spectrophotometer using 1 cm. quartz cells. Infrared spectra were taken on Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer.

The following substituted ethyl indole-2-carboxylates were prepared according to literature methods, viz., 4-chloro-(Ia⁹), 5-chloro-(Ib¹⁰), 6-chloro-(Ic¹⁰), 7-chloro-(Id¹⁰), 5-bromo-(Ie¹¹), 7-bromo-(If¹²), 5-methyl-7-chloro-(Ig³), 5-chloro-7-methyl-(Ih³) and 5-bromo-7-methyl-(Ii³).

2-Hydroxymethylindoles (II)

A solution of ethyl 4-chloroindole-2-carboxylate (5 g.) in dry ether (100 ml.) was added dropwise to a well stirred suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (1.5 g.) in dry ether (100 ml.). After complete addition it was stirred for an hour more at room temperature. Excess of lithium aluminium hydride was decomposed carefully by adding water (1.5 ml.), sodium hydroxide (15%; 1.5 ml.) and finally water (3 ml.). The white precipitate was filtered off and washed several times with small portions of fresh ether, the total filtrate was washed with water and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate, solvent distilled off and the residue crystallised from suitable solvent. The various 2-hydroxymethylindoles, similarly prepared, are described in Table 1.

Indole-2-carboxaldehydes (III)

To a solution of 4-chloro-2-hydroxymethylindole (4 g.) in dichloromethane (250 ml.) was added activated manganese dioxide (10 g.) and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 12–15 hr. The oxidation reaction was followed by t.l.c. till the spot due to 2-hydroxymethylindole disappeared. Whenever necessary, fresh quantity of activated manganese dioxide (2–3 g.) was added. The reaction mixture was filtered and the residual manganese dioxide was washed several times with small quantity of fresh dichloromethane. Total filtrate was collected and the solvent removed by distillation, to get the crude 4-chloroindole-2-carboxaldehyde as a pale-yellow solid, which was purified by crystallisation. The indole-2-carboxaldehydes similarly prepared are described in Table 2.

2-(2-Nitrovinyl) indoles (IV) :

A solution of 4-chloroindole-2-carboxaldehyde (2.0 g.) and nitromethane (3.0 g.) in methanol (50 ml.) was cooled to -5° . Ice cold aqueous sodium hydroxide (15 ml., 50%) was added dropwise at 0° or below, while the reaction mixture was stirred vigorously. A white precipitate separated after one hour. The contents of the flask were poured over crushed ice (400 g.) containing concentrated hydrochloric acid (30 ml.). The orange precipitate which separated out was collected, washed with water, dried and crystallised from suitable solvent. The various

TABLE I -2-HYDROXYMETHYLINDOLES (II)

Sl No.	2-hydroxy-methylindole	Molecular formula	M.P. (°C)	Rf.*	u.v. spectra (EtOH)		i.r. spectra** (cm ⁻¹) (Nujol)		Analysis %					
					m μ	log ϵ	ν OH/NH	Found			Required			
								C	H	N	C	H	N	
IIa	4-Chloro-	C ₉ H ₈ NOCl	76	0.607	227 279	4.231 4.020	3535 m 3250 ms	59.85	4.73	7.66	59.54	4.41	7.72	
IIb	5-Chloro-	C ₉ H ₈ NOCl	116	0.616	230 281	4.345 3.835	3405 sh 3320 m	59.81	4.10	7.50	59.54	4.41	7.72	
IIc	6-Chloro-	C ₉ H ₈ NOCl	143	0.764	...	...	3390 sh 3150 br	59.13	4.70	8.00	59.54	4.41	7.72	
IId	7-Chloro-	C ₉ H ₈ NOCl	80	0.674	230 273	4.295 4.350	3340 ms	59.58	3.89	7.41	59.54	4.41	7.72	
IIe	5-Bromo-	C ₉ H ₈ NOBr	117	0.628	227 284	4.390 3.845	3418 sh 3320 br	47.30	4.10	6.16	47.80	3.54	6.19	
IIf	7-Bromo-(picrate derivative)	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₅ O ₈ Br	203 (decomp.)	...	...	...	...	...	...	12.09	...	...	12.31	
IIg	5-Methyl-7-chloro-	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ NOCl	97	0.631	225 274	4.464 3.947	3448 sh 3318 br	60.97	5.60	7.08	61.42	5.12	7.16	
IIh	5-Chloro-7-methyl-	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ NOCl	118	0.764	228 274	4.256 3.710	...	61.94	4.90	7.43	61.42	5.12	7.16	
IIi	5-Methyl-7-bromo-	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ NOBr	93	0.631	225 275	4.423 3.950	3438 sh 3330 br	50.11	4.20	5.81	50.01	4.17	5.83	

* TLC (Silica gel G, ethylacetate)

** m = medium, s = strong, sh = sharp, br = broad.

TABLE 2—INDOLE-2-CARBOXALDEHYDES (III)

Sl No.	Indole-2-carboxaldehyde	Molecular formula	M.P. (°C)	Rf.*	u.v. spectra (CHCl ₃)		i.r. spectra** (cm ⁻¹) (Nujol)		Analysis %					
					m μ	log ϵ	ν NH	ν C = O	Found			Required		
									C	H	N	C	H	N
IIIa	4-Chloro-	C ₉ H ₈ NOCl	193	0.557	247 310	4.060 4.374	3308 ms	1675 s	60.23	3.40	8.30	60.19	3.34	7.80
IIIb	5-Chloro-	C ₉ H ₈ NOCl	216	0.540	247 308	3.970 4.370	3279 m	1667 s	59.83	3.40	8.10	60.19	3.34	7.80
IIIc	6-Chloro-	C ₉ H ₈ NOCl	175	0.598	245 317	3.843 4.270	3275 m	1667 s	59.92	3.00	7.58	60.19	3.34	7.80
IIId	7-Chloro-	C ₉ H ₈ NOCl	148	0.770	245 305	3.963 4.315	3289 ms	1672 s	59.90	3.00	7.58	60.19	3.34	7.80
IIIe	5-Bromo-	C ₉ H ₈ NOBr	220	0.557	246 311	3.990 4.312	3290 ms	1660 s	48.67	2.90	6.47	48.23	2.68	6.25
IIIf	7-Bromo-	C ₉ H ₈ NOBr	135	0.713	247 307	4.090 4.390	3328 ms	1675 s	48.71	3.10	6.66	48.23	2.68	6.25
IIIg	5-Methyl-7-chloro-	C ₁₀ H ₈ NOCl	124	0.700	248 308	4.022 4.355	3318 ms	1665 s	62.32	4.28	7.51	62.04	4.14	7.24
IIIh	5-Chloro-7-methyl-	C ₁₀ H ₈ NOCl	188	0.564	248 311	4.105 4.360	3348 ms	1675 s	62.41	4.37	7.53	62.04	4.14	7.24
IIIi	5-Methyl-7-bromo-	C ₁₀ H ₈ NOBr	119	0.721	246 309	4.150 4.480	3330 ms	1675 s	50.71	3.50	5.59	50.44	3.44	5.58

* TLC [Silica gel G, ethylacetate-chloroform (1 : 19)]

** m = medium, s = strong.

TABLE 3—2-(2-NITROVINYL)INDOLES (IV)

Sl. No.	2-(2-Nitrovinyl) indole	Molecular formula	M.P. (°C)	u.v. spectra (EtOH)		i.r. spectra* (Nujol)		Analysis %					
				m μ	log ϵ	ν NH	ν N $\begin{matrix} \nearrow O \\ \searrow O \end{matrix}$	Found			Required		
								C	H	N	C	H	N
IVa	4-Chloro	C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	198	220 260 386	4.270 3.980 4.380	3378 ms	1240 w 1265 w 1290 m	53.68	3.50	12.35	53.95	3.15	12.59
IVb	5-Chloro	C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	192-3	...	...	...	...	54.38	3.40	12.35	53.95	3.15	12.59
IVc	6-Chloro	C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	221	218 259 394	4.280 3.945 4.340	3370 m	1225 m 1285 m	54.21	3.00	12.80	53.95	3.15	12.59
IVd	7-Chloro	C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	210	219 260 382	4.210 3.930 4.335	3378 sh	1250 m 1280 m	53.98	3.08	12.73	53.95	3.15	12.59
IVe	5-Bromo	C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₂ O ₂ Br	191-2	220 265 388	4.375 4.144 4.400	3398 m	1235 w 1282 m	45.10	2.58	10.31	44.95	2.62	10.49
IVf	7-Bromo	C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₂ O ₂ Br	196-7	218 255 379	4.270 4.080 4.440	3398 ms	1240 w 1260 m	45.30	3.10	10.20	44.95	2.62	10.49
IVg	5-Methyl-7-chloro	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	214 (decomp.)	220 265 388	4.275 4.020 4.410	3378 ms	1212 m 1262 w 1300 ms	56.16	4.15	11.43	55.85	3.81	11.85
IVh	5-Chloro-7-methyl	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	221 (decomp.)	224 260 391	4.370 4.073 4.420	3375 ms	1228 w 1265 w 1290 ms	55.31	4.10	11.68	55.85	3.81	11.85
IVi	5-Methyl-7-bromo	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ Br	216 (decomp.)	...	...	...	...	46.66	2.90	9.59	46.99	3.20	9.97

* w = weak, m = medium, s = strong, sh = sharp.

TABLE 4—2-(2-AMINOETHYL)INDOLES (V)

Sl. No.	2-(2-Aminoethyl) indole	Molecular formula	M.P.* (°C)	Analysis %					
				Found			Required		
				C	H	N	C	H	N
Va	4-Chloro-(a) Oxalate	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ Cl	143	61.41	5.30	14.20	61.73	5.66	14.41
		C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	186-7(d)	...	...	9.21	...	...	9.45
Vb	5-Chloro-(b) Oxalate	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ Cl	95-6	61.45	5.31	14.28	61.73	5.66	14.41
		C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	220 (d)	...	...	9.80	...	...	9.45
Vc	6-Chloro-(c) Oxalate	...	Semisolid	...	...	...	...	...	...
		C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	193 (d)	...	...	9.55	...	...	9.45
Vd	7-Chloro-(d) Oxalate	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ Cl	204	61.98	6.10	14.72	61.73	5.66	14.41
		C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	219 (d)	...	...	9.42	...	...	9.45
Ve	5-Bromo-(e) Oxalate	...	Semisolid	...	...	...	...	...	...
		C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₄ Br	230 (d)	...	...	8.11	...	...	8.51
Vf	7-Bromo-(f) Oxalate	...	Semisolid	...	...	...	...	...	...
		C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₄ Br	210 (d)	...	...	8.83	...	...	9.38
Vg	5-Methyl-7-chloro-(g) Oxalate	...	Semisolid	...	...	...	...	...	...
		C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	211 (d)	...	...	8.96	...	...	9.38
Vh	5-Chloro-7-methyl-(h) Oxalate	...	Semisolid	...	...	...	...	...	...
		C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	215 (d)	...	...	8.95	...	...	8.18
Vi	5-Methyl-7-bromo-(i) Oxalate	...	Semisolid	...	...	...	...	...	...
		C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄ Br	213 (d)	...	...	8.61	...	...	...

d = decomposes.

TABLE 5—2-(2-NITROPROPENYL) INDOLES (VI)

Sl. No.	2-(2-Nitropropenyl)-indole	Molecular formula	M.P.* (°C)	u.v. spectra (EtOH)		i.r. spectra** (Nujol)		Analysis %					
				m μ	log ϵ	ν NH	ν N $\begin{matrix} \nearrow 70 \\ \searrow 60 \end{matrix}$	Found			Required		
								C	H	N	C	H	N
VIa	4-Chloro-	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	230-1	225 275 390	4.35 4.05 3.29	3270 br	1265 s	55.64	4.00	11.92	55.85	3.81	11.85
VIb	5-Chloro-	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	208-9(d)	222 278 388	4.02 4.14 3.14	3320 m	1220 m 1265 w 1295 s	56.13	4.10	11.61	55.85	3.81	11.85
VIc	7-Chloro-	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	158-9	225 259 380	4.24 4.86 4.17	3340 sh	1220 w 1295 s	55.61	4.10	12.10	55.85	3.81	11.85
VIe	5-Bromo-	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ Br	200(d)	225 260 390	4.32 3.88 4.27	3320 m	1220 w 1290 s	46.74	3.60	9.48	46.99	3.00	9.97
VI f	7-Bromo-	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ Br	161	225 256 380	4.33 4.02 4.25	3360 ms	1225 w 1305 s	46.47	3.28	10.20	46.99	3.00	9.97
VIg	5-Methyl-7-chloro-	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	193	225 259 387	4.28 3.88 4.17	...	...	57.02	4.11	11.10	57.51	4.39	11.21
VIh	5-Chloro-7-methyl-	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	180-1	225 265 399	4.42 4.073 4.08	3340 m	1290 s	57.12	4.51	11.53	57.51	4.39	11.21
VIi	5-Methyl-7-bromo-	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ Br	202	221 260 385	4.42 4.04 4.295	3350 m	1225 m 1285 ms	48.24	3.30	9.40	48.85	3.73	9.50

* d = decomposes

** w = weak, m = medium, s = strong, sh = sharp, br = broad.

TABLE 6—2-(2-AMINOPROPYL) INDOLES (VII)

Sl. No.	2-(2-aminopropyl) indole	Molecular formula	M.P.* (°C)	Analysis %					
				round			Required		
				C	H	N	C	H	N
VIIa	4-Chloro- (a) Oxalate	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ Cl	91	63.73	6.41	13.75	63.34	6.24	13.44
		C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	175-6 (d)	...	...	9.72	...	...	9.38
VIIb	5-Chloro- (b) Oxalate	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ Cl	191	63.31	6.20	12.95	63.34	6.24	13.44
		C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	205 (d)	...	...	9.68	...	...	9.38
VIIc	7-Chloro- (c) Oxalate	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ Cl	94	63.89	6.30	13.34	63.34	6.24	13.44
		C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	93-4 (d)	...	...	9.81	...	...	9.38
VIIe	5-Bromo- (e) Oxalate		Semisolid	...	...	...	...	...	...
		C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄ Br	221-3 (d)	...	...	8.41	...	...	8.17
VII f	7-Bromo-	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ Br	113	52.20	5.11	10.78	52.20	5.14	11.10
VIIg	5-Methyl-7-chloro- (g) Oxalate	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ N ₂ Cl	130	64.46	6.25	12.65	64.74	6.74	12.88
		C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	285 (d)	...	...	8.39	...	...	8.97
VIIh	5-Chloro-7-methyl- (h) Oxalate	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ N ₂ Cl	113	65.21	7.10	12.41	64.74	6.74	12.88
		C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	89-90 (d)	...	...	8.43	...	...	8.97
VIIi	5-Methyl-7-bromo- (i) Oxalate		Semisolid	...	...	...	...	...	...
		C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ Br	197-9 (d)	...	...	8.10	...	...	7.85

* d = decomposes.

nitrovinylindoles similarly prepared, are described in Table 3.

2-(2-Aminoethyl) indoles (V) :

4-Chloro-2-(2-nitrovinyl) indole (1 g.) in dry ether (100 ml.) was added dropwise to a slurry of lithium aluminium hydride (1.5 g.) in dry ether (100 ml.), with rapid stirring. The mixture was gently refluxed for 10 hr. Excess lithium aluminium hydride was decomposed by dropwise addition of water (1.5 ml.), aqueous sodium hydroxide (1.5 ml., 15%) and water (3 ml). The white precipitate was filtered off and was washed several times with small portions of fresh ether. The combined filtrate was washed with water, dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. Removal of solvent by distillation, furnished 4-chloro-2-(2-aminoethyl) indole, which was then converted into its oxalate derivative. The various 2-(2-aminoethyl)-indoles and their oxalates similarly prepared are described in Table 4.

2-(2-Nitropropenyl) indoles (VI) :

A mixture of 4-chloroindole-2-carboxaldehyde (1 g.), ammonium phosphate (1 g.), glacial acetic acid (2.5 ml.) and nitroethane (2.5 ml.), was heated under reflux for 25-30 min. On cooling, shining dark red crystals separated. The crystals were collected, washed with little ether and then thoroughly with warm water and dried. Crystallisation of the product from suitable solvent gave 4-chloro-2-(2-nitropropenyl) indole as orange flat needles. The various 2-(2-nitropropenyl) indoles similarly prepared are described in Table 5.

2-(2-Aminopropyl) indoles (VII) :

A solution of 4-chloro-2-(2-nitropropenyl) indole (1 g.) in dry ether (60 ml.) was added dropwise to a

slurry of lithium aluminium hydride (1.5 g.) in dry ether (100 ml.). The reaction mixture was gently refluxed for 8 hr. and was then worked up according to the procedure described for (V) above. The product was crystallised and converted into oxalate derivative. The various 2-(2-aminopropyl)-indoles and their oxalate derivatives are described in Table 6.

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